

Disulphuric Acid Solvent System

RAM CHAND PAUL* and V. P. KAPILA**

Strong protonic acids constitute a very important group in the fast developing field of non-aqueous solvents. One can mention a few like sulphuric¹, chlorosulphuric², fluorosulphuric³ and disulphuric acids and liquid hydrogen fluoride¹ as strong protonic acids. Of these, liquid hydrogen fluoride and sulphuric acid have been investigated quite extensively. During the last few years, investigations on fluorosulphuric and disulphuric acids have been undertaken in view of the fact that perhaps they are the strongest acids known. The present review is an attempt to give a brief account of the work that has been accomplished in disulphuric acid.

1. Disulphuric Acid :

DISULPHURIC acid, H₂S₂O₇, can be easily had in a state of purity and corresponds to a phase melting at 35.11°C (Table 1) having composition, 44.49% SO₃w/w, in the H₂SO₄ - SO₃ system. Auerbach⁴ was the first to show interest in disulphuric acid and he measured its heat of fusion and also reported the behaviour of elemental sulphur, selenium and tellurium in it while Robles and Moles⁵ studied the solubilities of a few organic compounds.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF DISULPHURIC ACID

Property	Value
Freezing point	35.11°
Density	1.9686 gm/c.c.
Viscosity	74.86 C. P.
Heat of fusion	5.67 kcal/mole
Specific conductivity	3.707 × 10 ⁻² ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Cryoscopic constant	5.90 deg. mole ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹
Dielectric constant	47
H ₀	-12.2
K _i	3.6 × 10 ⁻³

* Equilibrium constant for ionic self-dissociation.

2. Cryoscopy in Disulphuric Acid :

Due to its convenient freezing point disulphuric acid has been profitably used for cryoscopic investigations.

It has been reported^{6,7} that the solutes, sulphuryl chloride, disulphuryl chloride, trisulphuryl chloride, trisulphuryl fluoride, fluorosulphuric acid, chlorosulphuric acid, trifluoroacetic acid, trinitrobenzene and trinitrotoluene are all soluble in H₂S₂O₇ and behave as non-electrolytes. These solutes have been shown to give linear freezing-point depression curves upto 0.2 m in H₂S₂O₇. The slopes of the curves correspond to 5.9 deg mole⁻¹ kg, the molal depression coefficient (K_f). This value for K_f agrees very well with the value given by Dacre and Wyatt⁸ from their measurement of heat of fusion.

For a reaction of the type,

* Vice-Chancellor, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160014.

** Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh 160014.

were P,Q,R, etc., are the new species formed and p,q,r, etc., are the molal concentrations of these species. it is possible to show that⁹

$$p + q + r + \dots = \nu = \frac{B(1 - 0.178 \text{ ms})}{K_f \times m} \quad \dots (ii)$$

where B=depression in freezing point,

m = molality of the solute, A.

and s is the number of moles of H₂S₂O₇ taking part in the reaction.

Thus ν can be safely defined as the number of moles of all the particles (charged or neutral), except those which are specific to the solvent self-dissociation, produced per mole of a solute, A.

The accurate assessment of B is sometimes difficult due to the large amount of super cooling that this solvent undergoes. Therefore, it is essential to apply a correction to the observed freezing point. This correction factor, δ, has been empirically expressed by the relationship :

$$\delta = 0.014 B b \quad \dots (iii)$$

where b is the amount of supercooling.

The formation of H₂S₂O₇ from sulphuric acid and sulphur trioxide is evident from Figure 1, which represents a phase diagram of the two component system, H₂SO₄ - SO₃, (composition against temperature (freezing point of the mixture)).

The two arms of the freezing point curve (Figure-1) represent the depression in freezing point produced due to the presence of excess of SO₃ and H₂SO₄ in H₂S₂O₇, respectively. Since the two components react to give H₂S₂O₇ quantitatively, each can be estimated by titrating the mixture with the other component to the maximum freezing point. The moles of H₂SO₄ produced per mole of a solute (estimated by adding SO₃) is denoted by 'c'.

FIG.1- The Freezing-point phase diagram of $H_2SO_4-SO_3$ system in the region of the composition $H_2S_2O_7$

A and A', Freezing-point curve for non-electrolyte ($\nu=1$) dissolved in hypothetical undissociated solvent.
 C and C', Freezing-point curves for H_2SO_4 and SO_3 respectively calculated assuming self dissociation according to equation (iv)
 E, Experimental freezing point curve.
 (From Ref.-6)

2.1. Self-Dissociation Equilibria in Disulphuric Acid:

The broad maximum observed in the freezing point curve in the region of the composition, $H_2S_2O_7$, (Figure 1) is indicative of its extensive self-dissociation as under :

Gillespie and Robinson⁹ and Walrafen¹⁰ have examined Raman spectra of disulphuric acid and have shown the existence of the species, $H_2S_3O_{10}$. By selecting an appropriate freezing point for the hypothetical undissociated solvent (41°C) the equilibrium constant for solvent self-dissociation, K_d^6 , has been approximated to be 0.25 mole² litre⁻². Since the experimental freezing point curve for SO_3 ('E' in Figure 1) has a lower slope than that expected in view of equilibrium (iv), other additional modes of self-dissociation involving higher polysulphuric acids have been contemplated. On this basis, the existence of the species like $H_2S_4O_{13}$ and $H_2S_5O_{16}$, etc., has also been suggested. The self-dissociation equilibria involving the formation of the latter can, however, be neglected for all practical purposes because of the small quantities of these involved. The concentrations of various species in $H_2S_2O_7$ are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—CONCENTRATION OF VARIOUS SPECIES IN PURE DISULPHURIC ACID

Species	Concentration
H_2SO_4	0.57 m
$H_2S_3O_{10}$	0.29 m
$H_2S_4O_{13}$	0.14 m
H_2SO_4	0.06 m
$HS_3O_{10}^-$	0.06 m
$H_2S_5O_{17}$	4.47 m

The fact that the pure solvent has a high specific conductivity ($3.7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, Table 1) clearly shows that there is an ample concentration of ionic species present in the solvent. Obviously, these ionic species are a consequence of solvent self-ionisation. As $H_2S_3O_{10}$ is a stronger acid than $H_2S_2O_7$, its participation in self-ionization of the solvent has been conjectured as below⁶ :

That the equilibrium (v) above represents the actual mode of self-ionization is deduced from the freezing point depression produced by metal sulphates in disulphuric acid⁶. Their mode of ionization is given as under :

It has been observed that the solutions of the mono-valent sulphates in disulphuric acid do not have identical freezing-point-depression curves at concentrations higher than 0.08 m. Instead the freezing point-depression produced by them increases in the following order :

which is also the order in which their conductivities increase at a given concentration. Both these effects are attributed in part to ion-pair formation.⁶

In the case of Li_2SO_4 a cryoscopic titration against SO_3 reveals the formation of less than 3 moles of sulphuric acid implying that the equilibrium,

remains on the left hand side. Therefore, lithium sulphate ionises as⁶ :

Due to its greater charge density the anion, $HS_2O_7^-$, has been preferred over $HS_3O_{10}^-$ for chelation with Li^+ . Thus Gillespie and Malhotra⁶ have divided the cations into two groups, Li^+ and the rest. A comparison of equations (vi) and (viii) shows that cations having smaller size would prefer to ionize in a fashion similar to that of Li_2SO_4 . However, the reaction involving $HS_2O_7^-$ species is of little consequence for the cations which are larger than Li^+ and constitute the second

group. The equilibrium constant for the ionic-self dissociation (Table 1) has been computed from the freezing point depression produced by metal sulphates.

FIG.2 - Conductivities of solutions of metal sulphates in disulphuric acid

A. M_2SO_4 conductivities plotted against the molality of $HS_3O_{10}^-$
(From Ref 6)

At low concentrations the metal sulphates have very similar conductivities, hinting at the nominal contribution made by the cations towards overall conductance. A plot of specific conductivity vs the total

concentration of $HS_3O_{10}^-$ extrapolates to zero conductance at zero concentration of the anion specific to the solvent ($HS_3O_{10}^-$, Figure 2). The two observations are in accordance with the proposition that $HS_3O_{10}^-$ is the most mobile anion in $H_2S_2O_7$. In view of the large size of $HS_3O_{10}^-$ and the high viscosity of disulphuric acid it is believed that $HS_3O_{10}^-$ conducts by means of a proton-jump mechanism.⁶

2. 2 Significance of γ , ν and c Factors⁶ :

In order to trace the course of a reaction in disulphuric acid it is essential to evaluate three parameters, γ , ν and c . γ is the number of moles of $HS_3O_{10}^-$ ions produced per mole of a solute. As sulphuric acid is a weak base of disulphuric acid solvent system, its appearance in the reaction products shall produce a certain amount of $HS_3O_{10}^-$ ions in excess over those produced by the solute. And this will lead to an erroneous judgement of the γ factor. A set of conductivity calibration curves, (Figure 3), have therefore been constructed to evaluate the γ value of a solute.

Nitromethane behaves as a simple base (curves B, Figure 3)

The curves A, C and D have been constructed by adding or subtracting the conductance due to $H_2S_2O_4$. The curves E, F and G have similarly been approximated on the basis of ionisation of K_2SO_4 which ionises according to equation (vi). The γ value of an unknown electrolyte can now be adjudged by reference to one of these calibration curves.

Gillespie and Malhotra (loc. cit) have also constructed calibration curves for freezing point depression,

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
$HS_3O_{10}^-$	$HS_3O_{10}^- + H_2SO_4$	$HS_3O_{10}^- + 2H_2SO_4$	$HS_3O_{10}^- + 3H_2SO_4$	$2HS_3O_{10}^-$	$2HS_3O_{10}^- + 2H_2SO_4$	$2HS_3O_{10}^- + 4H_2SO_4$
1	1	2	3	2	2	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	0

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
$X^+ + HS_3O_{10}^-$	$X^+ + HS_3O_{10}^- + H_2SO_4$	$X^+ + HS_3O_{10}^- + 2H_2SO_4$	$X^+ + HS_3O_{10}^- + 3H_2SO_4$	$X^+ + HS_3O_{10}^- + Y + H_2SO_4$	$X^+ + HS_3O_{10}^- + Y + 2H_2SO_4$	$2X^+ + 2HS_3O_{10}^- + 2H_2SO_4$	$2X^+ + 2HS_3O_{10}^- + 4H_2SO_4$
1	1	2	3	1	2	2	2
0	1	2	2	3	3	4	4

Fig. 3. Calibrated conductivity and freezing point curves in disulphuric acid for the general reaction,
Solute + $H_2S_2O_7 \rightarrow aX^+ + aHS_3O_{10}^- + b\gamma + cH_2SO_4$
(From Ref. 11)

which may be used directly to evaluate the γ value of a solute. c , which may be conveniently defined as the moles of sulphuric acid produced per mole of a solute, can be ascertained cryoscopically by titration against sulphur trioxide as already emphasized in the ionisation of metal sulphates.

2.3 Evaluation of ionisation Equilibria for Weak Electrolytes¹¹.

The equilibria pertaining to self-dissociation and self-ionisation of the pure solvent having been established, it is possible to give a quantitative treatment to the ionisation of weak electrolytes, using the relationship,

$$K_b = [\text{HS}_2\text{O}_{10}]^- / (1-\alpha) \quad (\text{x})$$

where α is the degree of dissociation of the weak electrolyte and $[\text{HS}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ is the total concentration of $\text{HS}_2\text{O}_{10}^-$ including that resulting from solvent self-ionization.

3. Acids and Bases in Solvosystem Disulphuric Acid :

In view of the solvosystem concept, a solute which enhances directly or indirectly the concentration of $\text{HS}_2\text{O}_{10}^-$ or H_2SO_4^+ ions is a base or an acid of disulphuric acid solvent system respectively. In order to determine whether a solute is acting as an acid or a base, an external standard base is added to the solution. If there is an increase in the conductance, the solute under consideration is a base and the increase in conductance is due to the production of $\text{HS}_2\text{O}_{10}^-$ ions by the external base. However, if on the other hand, there is a decrease in conductance, the solute in question is an acid of the system and the fall in conductance is attributable to the following acid-base reaction :

3.1 Acids :

On account of the strong protonic nature of disulphuric acid the majority of the solutes behave as bases in it. The solutes which can act as acids have to be stronger acids than disulphuric acid and are, therefore, restricted in number.

The species of the type, $\text{H}_m\text{M}(\text{HSO}_4)_n$, are so strongly acidic that they ionise to generate H_2SO_4^+ ions and are thus acids of disulphuric acid solvent system. M is represented by the elements boron, titanium and tin. The acids, $\text{H}_m\text{M}(\text{HSO}_4)_n$, are obtained 'in situ' by the solvolysis of the corresponding metal halides, or oxides¹²⁻¹⁴ e.g.,

Boric anhydride, B_2O_3 , is solvolysed in disulphuric acid to tetrahydrogensulphatoboric acid, $\text{HB}(\text{HSO}_4)_4$, which acts as a strong acid¹⁴ :

this fact is well borne out in Figure 4 which contains the acid base titration of B_2O_3 vs nitromethane and acetic acid.

In Figure 4 the end point is locatable at base : acid ratio of 2 : 1. Nevertheless, if the figure is viewed a bit critically one would find that the minimum is reached a little earlier in the case of acetic acid than with that of nitromethane, both of which have a γ value of 1 (equations xxvi and ix respectively). Sulphuric acid is a weak base in disulphuric acid (section 5.1). Therefore, as the quantity of H_2SO_4 produced in a reaction increases the quantity of $\text{HS}_2\text{O}_{10}^-$ generated will also increase and thus the neutralisation point will shift accordingly. It has also been reported that at concentrations higher than 0.2m, the solutions of the boron compounds, viz., BCl_3 , B_2O_3 , etc., exhibit a lower value of the ν factor than that predicted by equations xii, xiv, etc. This decrease in the ν value has been ascribed to the polymerization of the species, $\text{B}(\text{HSO}_4)_4^-$, through sulphate bridging.

FIG. 4- Conductometric titration curves in disulphuric acid (From Ref.-14)

Unlike BCl_3 and BBr_3 , TiCl_4 and SnCl_4 have been reported to possess poor solubilities (0.14 m). At higher concentrations a yellow and a white compound precipitates out in the case of TiCl_4 and SnCl_4 respectively. The high viscosity of the solvent has hindered the isolation of the compounds. The solutions are, however, acidic with respect to $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ solvent system.

An acid base titration with KHSO_4 reveals a break in the conductance curve at molar ratio of $\text{KHSO}_4/\text{MCl}_4$ equal to 1 : 1. The neutralization reaction has been represented as given by equation xvi-a¹².

Antimony(V) chloride behaves in an analogous fashion,¹²

but a lower value of $\nu (=6.4)$ implies that the equilibrium,

does not lie completely to the right suggesting that the acid, $\text{H}[\text{Sb}'\text{HSO}_4)_6]$, is a weak acid of $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ solvent system. The chances of polymerization through sulphate bridging are not remote in this case too.

Antimony(V) fluoride, however, does not undergo complete solvolysis but still acts as an acid of the solvo-system disulphuric acid¹².

Uranium(VI) chloride is the only metal halide which does not act as an acid despite the fact that it is completely solvolyzed.¹⁵

In solutions having concentration higher than 0.1 m a precipitate, which probably consists of polymeric $[\text{U}(\text{HSO}_4)_6]_x$ units, is formed.

3.2 Bases :

All the solutes, except those mentioned in sections 3.1 and 6, behave as bases in disulphuric acid. The behaviour of metal sulphates (section 2.1) is a representative example of the behaviour of bases in disulphuric acid. Besides these, *p*-nitrotoluene, nitrobenzene, *p*-nitrochlorobenzene and 2,4-dinitrotoluene are fully protonated in a manner similar to that of CH_3NO_2 (equation ix). These solutes are referred to as 'standard' bases and the calibration curves (Figure 3) have been obtained from the conductance exhibited by the solutions of these compounds.

Some of the nitro compounds such as, *m*-nitrochlorobenzene, *m*-dinitrobenzene 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene and 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene are partly protonated and their dissociation constants, K_b 's, are 0.65, 0.26, 0.10 and 0.10 respectively.¹⁴

4. Organic Solutes :

A vast number of organic solutes, to be discussed in this section, behave as bases in disulphuric acid. In order to permit a proper comparison among different congeners, the organic solutes have been classified in a pragmatic fashion. These compounds have a basic nitrogen and/or an oxygen atom. Since organic compounds are identified only on the basis of their functional groups, the relevant discussion on these is subdivided in sections 4.1 to 4.8, accordingly. In as much as the number of organic compounds which have been examined in $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ is very large, only the representative compounds are being mentioned, while in respect of others, the γ , ν and c values are summarised in Table 3.

TABLE 3—A SUMMARY OF γ , ν AND c VALUES OF VARIOUS COMPOUNDS IN DISULPHURIC ACID

Compound	γ	ν	c
Phosphoryl fluoride	0	1	0
Seleninyl chloride	1	2	1
Acetone	0.81	1.7	?
Acetophenone	1	2	1
Benzophenone	1	2	1
4,4'-Dichlorobenzophenone	1	2	1
Methyl ethyl ketone	1	2	1
Methyl propyl ketone	1	2	1
Methyl isopropyl ketone	1	2	1
Methyl butyl ketone	1	2	1
Methyl isobutyl ketone	1	2	1
Benzil	1	2	1
Anthraquinone	1	2	1
<i>p</i> -Benzoquinone	1	2	1
Alizerin	1	2	1
Isatin	1	2	1
Acetyl acetone	1	2	1
Acetonyl acetone	1	2	1
Benzyl acetone	1	2	1
Dibenzoyl methane	> 1		
Urea	> 1		
Phenyl urea	1	2	1
Diphenyl urea	1	2	1
Tetram. thyl urea	2	4	2
Thiourea	> 1		
Phenyl thiourea	1	2	1
Diphenyl thiourea	2	4	2
Biurea	2	4	2
Biureat	2	4	2
Diethyl carbonate	1	2	1
Acetamide	1.6	3.8	2.8
Dimethyl formamide	1	2	1
N-methyl acetamide	1	2	1
N,N-dimethyl acetamide	1	2	1
Dioxan		unstable solution	
Tetrahydrofuran	1	2	1
Diphenyl ether	0.34	1.37	
Propionic acid	1	2	3
Butyric acid	1	2	3
Valeric acid	1	2	3
Mesitoic acid	1	2	3
Isovaleric acid	1	2	3

Table 3—Contd.

Table 3—Contd.

Compound	γ	ν	c
Caproic acid	1	2	3
Trifluoro acetic acid	0	1	0
Monochloro acetic acid	1	2	1
Dichloro acetic acid	<1		
Chloropropionic acid	1	2	1
2-Chloropropionic acid		unstable solution	
Triphenyl acetic acid	1	2	3
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	1	2	3
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	1	2	3
Mesitylic acid	1	2	3
2,3,5,6-Tetramethylbenzoic acid	1	2	3
2,3,4,5,6-Pentamethylbenzoic acid	1	2	3
Acetic anhydride	2	4	4
Propionic anhydride	2	4	4
Isobutyric anhydride	2	4	4
Monochloro acetic anhydride	2	3	2
Succinic anhydride	1	2	1
Phthalic anhydride	1	2	1
Maleic anhydride	1	2	1
Dimethyl sulphoxide	1	2	1
Diphenyl sulphoxide		unstable solution	
4-Nitro diphenyl sulphoxide	1	2	1
4,4'-Dinitrodiphenyl sulphoxide	1	2	1
Dimethyl sulphone	1	2	1
Diethyl sulphone	1	2	1
Dipropyl sulphone	1	2	1
Diphenyl sulphone	1	2	1
4-Nitro diphenyl sulphone	1	2	1
4,4'-Dinitro diphenyl sulphone	<1		
Sulphoane	1	2	1
Diethyl sulphate		very weak base	
Diphenyl sulphide	1	2	1
4-Nitrophenyl sulphide	1	2	1
4,4'-Dinitrophenyl sulphide	1	2	1
Dibenzoyl disulphide		unstable solution	
2,2'-Dinitrophenyl disulphide	2	3	2
2,2'-Diaminophenyl disulphide	2	3	2
4,4'-Dinitrophenyl disulphide	2	3	2
4,4'-Diaminophenyl disulphide	3	4	3
Methylalcohol	0.34	1.9	
Ethyl alcohol	0.34	1.9	
Propyl alcohol	0.51	2.14	
Butyl alcohol	0.82	2.24	
Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylcarbinol	1	2	3
Tri- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl carbinol	1	2	3
Tri- <i>o</i> -tolylcarbinol	1	2	3
Tri- <i>p</i> -nitrophenyl carbinol	1	2	3
Methyl trichloroacetate	0	1	0
Ethyl trichloroacetate	0	1	0
Methyl formate		unstable solution	
Ethyl chloroformate		unstable solution	
Ethylene glycol	<1	1.7	
Dichloro ethane	0	1	0
Ethylene dibromide		unstable solution	
3,10'-Diphenothiazinyl	2	3	2
Acetyl chloride	1	3	2
Benzoyl chloride	1	3	2
Butyryl chloride	1	3	2
Isobutyryl chloride	1	3	2
Isovaleryl chloride	1	3	2
Mesityl chloride	1	3	2
Trichloro acetyl chloride		unstable solution	
Oxalyl chloride		unstable solution	
Succinyl chloride	1	2	1
Tellurium (IV) bromide		unstable solution	

higher than 0.2m a white precipitate is formed and the conductance of the solution decreases a bit. It is believed that the formation of a ketone takes place which reacts with disulphuric acid in an unknown fashion. Other aromatic and aliphatic ketones are strong bases in disulphuric acid and due to the high acidity of the solvent they are all levelled to the basicity of the HS_2O_7^- ion¹⁶. The introduction of an electron withdrawing group (e.g., Cl) in the compound is also ineffective in reducing the basicity of the C=O group. In Table 3 the γ , ν and c factors of various ketones, in $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$, are given.

Solutions of diketones in disulphuric acid, however, have revealed that whenever the two carbonyl groups are adjacent or separated by a single methylene group, only monoprotonation occurs¹⁶ (Table 3).

The electron withdrawing inductive effect of the phenyl group is very much evident in the conductance of dibenzoyl methane which undergoes incomplete protonation.

However, the basicity of the C=O group is enhanced in the vicinity of a nitrogen atom, e.g., biurea accepts two protons.

Conductance and cryoscopic investigations of Paul and coworkers¹⁷ show that urea accepts more than one proton but not completely two while tetramethylurea accepts two protons or has two strong basic sites for protonation.

This observation is in line with the hypothesis that the (-CH₃) group exerts an electron donating effect. In contrast to this its phenyl- and diphenyl- derivatives are only monoprotonated. And that provides another convincing example in favour of the electron-withdrawing inductive effect of the phenyl ring.

4.1 Ketones, Diketones, Ureas and Amides :

Among the ketones, acetone exhibits an anomalous behaviour. No doubt it is singly protonated¹⁶ in disulphuric acid but in solutions having concentrations

The basicity of thioureas cannot be differentiated from the corresponding urea derivatives in disulphuric acid due to the protonation reaction in the two types of compounds taking place to almost the same extent¹⁷ (Table 3).

It has now been established that in the amides the oxygen atom is the site of protonation rather than the nitrogen atom¹. Formamide disproportionates into CO and NH₃ whereas acetamide gives acyl ion, as under¹⁷:

In contrast to these the N-alkyl acetamides undergo simple protonation reaction (equation ix). Their γ , ν and c values are listed in Table 3.

4.2 Acids and Acid Anhydrides :

Disulphuric acid is not only a strong protonic acid, but also a powerful dehydrating agent. Both these properties are manifested clearly in the solutions of aliphatic and aromatic monocarboxylic acids. Thus these acids dissolve in H₂S₂O₇ giving oxocarbonium ions¹⁸.

where R = an alkyl group, a phenyl group or a substituted phenyl group.

The i.r. spectrum indicates the presence of an RC⁺O cation in solution. Isobutyric acid is an exception to the general reaction given by equation xxvi. It gives a carbonium ion rather than an oxo-carbonium ion¹⁸;

a similar reaction has been described in the case of Ph₃CCOOH¹⁸, wherein the u.v./vis spectrum of the solution confirms the formation of the triphenylcarbonium ion. It is observed that the introduction of an electron withdrawing group in the aliphatic acids decreases the basicity of the -COOH group to permit only the protonation reaction to occur, whereas the substitution of such groups in the phenyl ring of benzoic acid has little effect in preventing the formation of the oxocarbonium ions. Thus monochloro- and dichloroacetic acids act as weak bases.

Formic acid reacts with disulphuric acid in a different way from the rest of its congeners¹⁸.

In Table 3 the γ , ν and c values in respect of other carboxylic acids are given.

Dicarboxylic acids constitute another interesting class of compounds that has been investigated in disulphuric acid¹⁸. If COOH(CH₂)_nCOOH is taken as the general formula of an aliphatic dicarboxylic acid it is found that the basicity of the COOH groups increases with increasing value to n, i.e., the number of intervening methylene groups. So, glutaric (n=3) and adipic (n=4) acids act as strong bidentate bases and are diprotonated, while malonic acid (n=1) accepts only one proton from disulphuric acid. Oxalic acid (n=0) is unstable and decomposes into CO, CO₂ and H₂O.

Anhydrides of monocarboxylic aliphatic acids do not act as simple bases. They are converted into the corresponding acyl ions in a fashion analogous to their parent acids¹⁴ (Table 3 for γ , ν and c). Nonetheless, the solvolytic reaction is arrested if an electron withdrawing group is present in the molecule, e. g., monochloroacetic anhydride is diprotonated (equation xxii). The anhydrides of dicarboxylic acids are monoprotanated (Table 3).

4.3 Sulphoxides, Sulphones, Sulphides etc :

Dimethyl sulphoxide acts as a monoacid base in disulphuric acid. Diphenyl sulphoxide, however, is sulphonated and thus could not be examined¹⁹. The introduction of nitro-group or groups in the phenyl ring protects the compound against sulphonation while the basicity of the S=O group remains unaltered. All such compounds are monoprotanated (Table 3).

Oxygen atoms in sulphones are slightly less basic than in the sulphoxides and they show resistance towards

TABLE 4—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF WEAK ELECTROLYTES IN H₂S₂O₇

Compound	10 ³ × K
Selenic acid	6.22
Methanesulphuric acid	6.46
Diffuorophosphoric acid	7.52
Sulphuric acid	2.40 ¹
Paratoluenesulphuric acid	12.46
Benzenesulphuric acid	9.28
m-Nitrochlorobenzene	0.65
m-Dinitrobenzene	0.26
2,4-Dinitrochlorobenzene	0.10
2,4-Dinitrofluorobenzene	0.10
4-Nitrodiphenyl sulphone	78.46
4,4'-Dinitrodiphenyl sulphone	60.92
Monochloroacetyl chloride	0.38
Dichloroacetyl chloride	0.015

sulphonation in disulphuric acid. Except the nitro-substituted aromatic sulphones, which are weak bases, all others are singly protonated¹⁹. The dissociation constants of weakly basic sulphones have been evaluated and are listed in Table 4.

The relative basicities of sulphides, disulphides and the stability of the S-S bond towards a highly acidic and an oxidising solvent, like disulphuric acid, have also been studied by Paul and coworkers¹⁹. They have found that most of the sulphides and disulphides give rise to unstable solutions due to side reactions (probably sulphonation). Due to the high acidity of the solvent, diphenyl sulphide and its nitro-derivatives are all levelled to the basicity of the HS₃O₁₀⁻ ion (Table 3). Among

the disulphides, 4,4'-diaminophenyldisulphide deserves a special mention as it forms a tripositive cation.

4.4 Alcohols :

Aliphatic alcohols are solvolysed to alkyl hydrogen sulphates¹⁸.

A higher conductance of the solution than what it should be due to one mole of sulphuric acid, emphasizes the weakly basic nature of the alkyl hydrogen sulphates. Paul and coworkers¹⁸ have reported that tert-butyl and n-octyl alcohols give coloured solutions and time dependent values of γ , ν and c , showing that a complicated

4.5 Esters :

In general, the behaviour of an ester in disulphuric acid reflects a chemical reaction which can be described as a composite of the behaviour of its constitutive alcohol and carboxylic acid. For example, the reactions given below¹⁸ are like those presented in sections 4.2 and 4.4 :

where R = CH₃, C₂H₅, C₃H₇, etc. ; R' = C₂H₅.

However, introduction of an electron withdrawing

group or atom stabilizes the ester which then acts as a simple base in disulphuric acid.

where R = CH₂Cl, CHCl₂ ; R' = C₂H₅, CH₃.

An analogous situation prevails among the esters of dicarboxylic acids. Thus dialkyl oxalates decompose²⁰ as under :

Whereas malonates behave as simple bases, e.g., diethylmalonate is monoprotonated²⁰.

But di-n-butyl malonate receives two protons.

reaction occurs. The exact nature of the reaction, however, remains unexplored.

The aromatic tertiary alcohols get dehydrated to the corresponding carbonium ions.

where X = CH₃, Cl, NO₂ or H.

4.6 Formation of Dipositive Carbonium Ions in Disulphuric Acid^{19,21} :

The strongly electrophilic nature of H₂S₂O₇ is expected to stabilize the weakly nucleophilic species. Therefore, Paul and coworkers (loc. cit.) have explored the possibility of stabilising a variety of carbonium ions in it. Tetraphenyl-p-xyleneglycol and tetraphenylphthalin are solvolysed to generate dipositive carbonium ions ; but trichloromethyl mesitylene provides only a

monopositive carbonium ion as represented below :

4.7 Acyl Halides :

The mode of reaction of an acyl halide, in disulphuric acid, is related in part to the behaviour of the parent acid in it. Accordingly, acetyl, benzoyl and n-butyrylchlorides form acyl ions and chlorosulphuric acid²²,

whereas acetyl bromide liberates free bromine.

The formation of an acyl ion is supported by the i.r. spectrum of the concentrated solutions of the acyl halides in disulphuric acid. Trichloroacetyl and oxalyl chlorides are unstable and chloro- and dichloroacetyl chlorides are weak bases²². The γ , ν and ϵ factors of the acyl halides are grouped with other compounds in Table 3.

4.8 Formation of sulphenium ion in $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$:²³

2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride dissolves and ionises in a way analogous to that of acetyl chloride, forming a unique sulphenium ion.

5. Inorganic Solutes in Disulphuric Acid :

The nature of the solutions of organic solutes leads us to a general observation that a protonation and/or a dehydration reaction are the commonest to be encoun-

tered in disulphuric acid. The inorganic solutes, as will be evident, usually experience solvolytic reactions which cannot be described as mere protonation reactions. Unlike some of the organic solutes, which present complications due to sulphonation, etc., the inorganic solutes give rise to stable solutions.

5.1 Acids and their Salts :

The behaviour of both the oxo and the binary acids has been studied in disulphuric acid and it is observed that none from either group is an acid of the system.

Both fluorosulphuric and chlorosulphuric acids are non-electrolytes in disulphuric acid¹⁴, although there is a small increase in conductance which may be a consequence of a decrease in the viscosity of the medium due to the addition of the solute. Sulphuric acid is a weak base and gives slightly conducting solutions⁹. Alternatively, the behaviour of disulphuric acid in sulphuric acid also emphasizes that sulphuric acid is only slightly protonated²⁴ :

perchloric¹², selenic, methanesulphuric, difluorophosphoric paratoluenesulphuric and benzenesulphuric acids are all weak bases and their slight protonation can be represented as under²⁵ :

Nitric acid, on the other hand, is dehydrated to nitronium ion¹¹.

Cacodylic, sulphamic¹⁷, phosphoric¹¹ and arsenic¹⁷ acids are fully protonated, e.g.

where M=P or As.

KCl and KF are solvolysed to the respective binary acids which react with the excess of SO₃ to give the corresponding halosulphuric acids¹¹.

where X=Cl or F.

The reaction of HBr with disulphuric acid is, nevertheless, out of tune with that of HCl or HF in that no bromosulphuric acid is formed, instead it is oxidized to free bromine which is a non-electrolyte²⁶ and imparts its peculiar colour to the solution.

KIO₃ has been studied instead of iodic acid due to the insolubility of the latter. The data of Gillespie and Malhotra¹² indicate that HIO₃, produced 'in situ' is dehydrated;

and at concentrations higher than 0.1m a white precipitate deposits, which they feel is the polymer, ((IO₂SO₄H)_x):

The dissociation constants of the weak bases in H₂S₂O₇ have been computed and are given in Table 4. On the basis of their extent of protonation in disulphuric acid, the relative acidities of some of the acids have been arranged in the following order:

5.2 Inorganic Acid Anhydrides:

Among the oxides of nitrogen, nitrous and nitric oxides produce non-conducting solutions¹⁴. Dinitrogen trioxide, dinitrogen tetroxide and dinitrogen pentoxide are solvolysed as given below:

The conductance and cryoscopic data have been supplemented by the i.r. spectrum which gives evidence of the formation of the various cations¹⁴. Phosphoric oxide, however, dehydrates H₂S₂O₇ to SO₃.

As₂O₃⁷ has a limited solubility (0.15 m) and at higher concentrations a compound, which cannot be isolated due to the high viscosity of the solvent, precipitates out of the solution. A low value of the cryoscopic factor, ν, has led Paul and coworkers (loc. cit.) to conjecture the formation of some polymeric compounds such as As₂O₃.SO₃, As₂O₃.2SO₃ or As₂O₃.SO₃.H₂S₂O₇, which may have the following structures:

The behaviour of B₂O₃, the anhydride of H₃BO₃, has already been presented in section 3.1.

Sulphur dioxide is a non-electrolyte in disulphuric acid. Selenium dioxide acts as a weak base in disulphuric acid (equation XLV) whereas tellurium dioxide is solvolysed to give H₂[Te(HSO₄)₆] which is a very weak acid²⁷.

The behaviour of sulphur trioxide in it has already been dealt with under section 2. Selenium trioxide does not alter the conductance of the solution, but the observed value of the cryoscopic factor, ν, has been best explained by the reaction given below:¹⁴

Sb₂O₃, Bi₂O₃ and As₂O₃ are insoluble in disulphuric acid.

5.3 Inorganic Halides :

The work of Paul and coworkers^{1,2,6} has revealed that disulphuric acid is an excellent solvent which enables one to distinguish between solutes having ionizable and non-ionizable halide ions. In the case of those solutes which possess ionizable halide ion or ions (fluorides or chlorides) the formation of halosulphuric acid takes place. However, bromides liberate bromine (equation XLVIII), rather than forming bromosulphuric acid, due to the oxidation of HBr. Alkali metal chlorides react with $H_2S_2O_7$ to produce a quantitative amount of HSO_3Cl .^{1,11}

Thallium(I), tin(II) and lead(II) chlorides ionize similarly.^{1,3}

where M = alkali metal, Tl, Sn or Pb ; X = Cl or F ;

n = valency.

$NOCl$, NO_2X (X = Cl or F)^{2,3} and S_4N_3Cl ^{2,3} have an exactly the same behaviour (equation LVII for n=1) giving rise to NO^+ , NO_2^+ and $S_4N_3^+$ cations respectively.

The solutes, $TeCl_4$, $SeCl_4$, PCl_5 and ICl_3 also react with disulphuric acid to produce HSO_3Cl as follows :^{2,6}

In the case of $BiCl_3$ ^{1,2}, the reaction occurs mainly on the pattern outlined by the above equation. But at concentrations equal to 0.08 m or higher, a white precipitate appears causing a small decrease in the conductance than that predicted by equation LVIII. The following tentative structure has been assigned to the insoluble polymeric compound :

As stated before, the bromides behave in different way, selenium (IV) and phosphorus (V) bromides, e. g., liberate free bromine.^{2,6}

There is another class of halides which do not have an ionizable halide ion, e. g., $POCl_3$, $POBr_3$ and PSX_3 (X = Cl, Br)^{2,2}. These compounds do not furnish chlorosulphuric acid or bromine when dissolved in disulphuric acid, instead they undergo a protonation reaction similar to that of nitromethane (equation ix). PCl_3 and PBr_3 are also included in this class of solutes which do not furnish an ionizable halide ion.^{2,2} These are oxidized to the corresponding phosphoryl halides which then act as strong mono-acid bases.

where X = Cl or Br.

There is still another class of compounds like SO_2Cl_2 , $S_2O_5Cl_2$, $S_3O_8Cl_2$, $S_3O_8F_2$ ⁶, $SOCl_2$ and $COCl_2$ ^{2,2}, which exclusively act as non-electrolytes. These solutes neither have an ionizable halide ion nor a sufficiently basic oxygen atom to accept a proton.

Sulphur dichloride and monochlorides of sulphur and selenium undergo a unique set of reactions which result in the formation of unusual cations.^{2,6}

5.4 Solvolysis of Miscellaneous Inorganic Compounds:

Triphenyl arsine and phosphine undergo oxidation with subsequent protonation.^{1,7}

where M = P or As

whereas the antimony and bismuth analogs are solvolyzed.

where M = Sb or Bi.

Benzenesulphuric acid is weakly basic in disulphuric acid. If this is accounted for (Section 5.1), $M(HSO_4)_3$ (M = Sb, Bi) are found to act as non-electrolytes.

A few vanadium (V), chromium (VI)^{2,8} and manganese (VII)^{2,9} compounds have also been investigated in disulphuric acid. Mishra and Symons^{9,0} proposed

the following reaction for V_2O_5 in 65% oleum :

Paul and coworkers (loc. cit.) reported that vanadium (V) oxide, which is sparingly soluble in disulphuric acid, gives a nonconducting solution. On the basis of cryoscopic investigations the reaction,

has been proposed. The existence of the species, $H[VO(HSO_4)_4]$, has been ascertained by comparing the u. v. spectrum (a broad band at 340 nm) of the solution with the solution of V_2O_5 in anhydrous sulphuric acid³¹. Similarly vanadyl chloride and ammonium meta vanadate also generates $H[VO(HSO_4)_4]$ species in disulphuric acid.

Paul and coworkers³² have recently studied the behaviour of potassium chromate and dichromate, which give highly conducting solutions in disulphuric acid. Their behaviour is found to be in accordance with the equations below :

Chromyl chloride forms a yellow compound when dissolved in disulphuric acid, which redissolves on shaking. From u. v. spectrum and conductance data the following reaction has been suggested :

Potassium permanganate, at low concentration, forms a green solution in disulphuric acid³³. At higher concentrations MnO_2 precipitates out with concomittant evolution of oxygen. The spectrum of $KMnO_4$ shows absorption bands at 250, 310, 460 and 650 nm. On the basis of the u. v./vis spectrum, conductance as well as the cryoscopic measurements the following reaction has been proposed :

The chemistry of various lead (IV) and tin (IV) compounds in disulphuric acid has also been studied³³. It has been reported that lead tetracetate dissolves in disulphuric acid to give a highly conducting solution. The solvolysis of lead (IV) acetate has been represented by the following equation :

However, the ν value of the solution is slightly more than 3 which emphasizes that $H_2[Pb(HSO_4)_6]$ is a weak acid, i.e., the equilibrium,

does not lie completely towards the right.

From the behaviour of various alkyl tin (IV) derivatives in disulphuric acid one may conclude that these experience only partial solvolysis. Thus tetrabutyl tin forms tributyl stannonium ion.

Trialkyl and dialkyl tin chlorides also undergo a similar reaction, as illustrated by the following equations :

Dialkyl and trialkyl tin oxides also experience partial solvolysis.

Malhotra and coworkers¹⁵ have also reported the solvolytic reactions of some uranium(VI) compounds in disulphuric acid. Uranium(VI) oxide is sparingly soluble in disulphuric acid but the solubility increases on heating (upto 45°) and the solutions of 0.06M concentration can be obtained without change in the conductance of the solution. The cryoscopic and conductance data are in favour of the following solvolytic reaction :

As the solvolyzed product is not soluble in the solvent, which is an indication of polymerization, the ν value decreases with increase in concentration.

Anhydrous uranyl sulphate, which has a limited solubility in disulphuric acid, can be dissolved to give solutions of 0.1m concentration, upon warming. U. V. and visible spectra of the yellow solutions are exactly the same as those reported for UO_2X_2 in solution and this suggests that the species involved in the two cases are of the same type. The following mode of reaction, for uranyl sulphate, is also supported by cryoscopic investigations :

Anhydrous uranyl formate and oxalate dissolve in disulphuric acid with the evolution of gases whereas uranyl acetate forms acyl ions (cf. behaviour of organic acids, section 4.2). At higher concentrations a yellow compound separates out from the solution. The modes of reactions of these compounds are represented as below :

6. Formation of Homoatomic Cations in Disulphuric Acid :

Disulphuric acid is one of the strongest protonic acids and is 10^9 times stronger than H_2SO_4 ³⁴. The presence of excess sulphur trioxide makes it a strong oxidising agent too. A strong oxidizing agent has the capability to produce an electrophilic species whereas the availability of a highly protonic medium conduces to their stability. Thus $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ is a good medium for producing and stabilizing different types of cations.

Sulphur trioxide has long been known to form a few interesting molecular addition compounds with the chalcogens. These have been assigned the formulae, S_2O_3 ³⁵, SeSO_3 ³⁶ and TeSO_3 ³⁷. In disulphuric acid the elements, S, Se and Te, dissolve giving highly coloured solutions. Detailed physico-chemical investigations have revealed the existence of some unusual cations in these solutions.

The dissolution of elemental sulphur in disulphuric acid gives rise to an intense blue colour^{38,39}. The blue colour slowly fades away, depending on the concentration of sulphur, to give colourless solutions. Though, the bulk susceptibility indicates the formation of a diamagnetic species, yet the e.s.r. spectrum indi-

cates a paramagnetic cation with 2 unpaired electrons.³⁸ The conductance and cryoscopic investigations of the blue and the colourless solutions along with the u. v./vis spectral data have led Paul and coworkers³⁹ to postulate the following set of reactions :

producing S_8^{+2} and S_4^{+2} cations rather than the species like S.SO_3 earlier postulated. Malhotra and coworkers⁴⁰ have isolated the compounds of sulphur, containing the unusual cations, with SO_3 , i.e., $\text{S}_4.S_3\text{O}_{10}$ and $\text{S}_8.S_4\text{O}_{13}$. These ionize in disulphuric acid according to the reactions given below :

On the basis of similar investigations Barr and coworkers⁴¹ have attributed the oxidation of selenium in disulphuric acid to the following reactions :

Paul and coworkers⁴² have isolated three different compounds of selenium with sulphur trioxide, viz., $\text{Se}_4\text{S}_4\text{O}_{18}$ (yellow), $\text{Se}_4\text{S}_3\text{O}_{10}$ (orange) and $\text{Se}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ (pale yellow). These compounds are soluble in disulphuric acid and their conductance and cryoscopic data indicate their solvolysis according to the following equations :

Solutions of elemental tellurium in disulphuric acid also exhibit a sequential colour change from red to colourless through yellow. It has been established⁴³ that the red solution is due to Te_4^{+2} cations.

and the yellow solution contains Te_2^{+2} cations.

In a manner analogous to that of selenium, two compounds of tellurium with sulphur trioxide of composition, $\text{Te}_4\text{S}_3\text{O}_{10}$ (reddish brown) and $\text{Te}_2\text{S}_3\text{O}_{10}$ (yellow) have been isolated⁴⁴. The following equation represents the solvolysis of $\text{Te}_4\text{S}_3\text{O}_{10}$ in $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$:

Table 5 lists the characteristic spectral (U.V./VIS.) bands of various cations in disulphuric acid.

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF UNUSUAL CATIONS IN DISULPHURIC ACID

Cation	Colour	max nm
S_8^{+3}	blue	590
S_4^{+3}	colourless	390
Se_6^{+2}	green	330
Se_4^{+2}	yellow	280
Te_4^{+2}	red	410
Te_2^{+2}	yellow	320
		520
		440
I_2	—	280
		380
		480
		640
		510
		420
I_3^+	—	300
As_4^{+3}	red	510
As_2^{+3}	yellow	380
		460
		380
P_8^{+3}	blue	260
		740
		560
P_4^{+3}	colourless	420
		350
Sb_3^{+3}	blue	280
		460
		680
Sb_2^{+3}	yellow	390
		310

The nature of the solutions of iodine in disulphuric acid complies with the formation of I_2^+ and I_3^+ cations⁴⁵ (Table-5). Approximately 64% of I_2 is oxidized to I_2^+ and the rest is converted into I_3^+ and $\text{I}(\text{HSO}_4)_2$. The formation of I_2^+ and I_3^+ has been ascribed to the following reactions⁴⁵ :

The compounds of I_2^+ , viz., $\text{I}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{I}_4\text{S}_3\text{O}_{10}$, have been isolated as stable solids. They immediately dissolve in disulphuric acid and are solvolysed⁴⁵.

Paul and coworkers^{46,47} have successfully attempted to stabilize the cations of group VB elements, in their uncommon oxidation states, in disulphuric acid. It has been found that nitrogen has a very poor solubility in the acid (<0.1 ml of gas per 100 ml of $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$) and that too can be got rid off on a little warming. There is no change in the conductance, suggesting that no reaction takes place, which is not unlikely in view of the extremely low basicity of the nitrogen molecule.

Considering the next element in the series, i.e., phosphorus, it is reported that red phosphorus is unattacked by disulphuric acid and even by strong oxidizing agents in disulphuric acid. Yellow phosphorus, however, floats and burns on the surface of the acid. In an atmosphere of CO_2 the element dissolves and gives a blue solution which turns yellow in a couple of days. Moreover, the change in colour, is irreversible with respect to a reducing or an oxidizing agent. On the basis of the electronic spectra of both the solutions (Table 5) it has been visualized that the blue solution possesses P_8^{+3} , and the colourless, P_4^{+3} cations.

The possibility of the existence of paramagnetic species like P_4^{+3} , P_8^{+3} , etc., has been rendered unlikely due to the diamagnetic nature of the solutions.

Arsenic is unattacked by $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ or sulphuric acid. At least in disulphuric acid, the oxide coating prevents any oxidation even in the presence of strong oxidizing agents such as KClO_4 or $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$. In sulphuric acid, on the other hand, a red colour develops in the presence of KClO_4 which persists on the addition of SO_3^{47} . The red colour slowly changes to yellow in the presence of an excess of oxidizing agent. The electronic spectra of both the solutions are summarised in Table 5. The spectrum of the red solution compares well with those of Te_4^{+2} and Se_4^{+2} and that of the yellow solution with Te_2^{+2} . After supplementing these observations with those from conductance and cryoscopic measurements the following reactions have been proposed :

Antimony presents a similar behaviour except that it goes directly in solution in disulphuric acid giving a white uncharacterised precipitate²⁵. It gets oxidized in H_2SO_4 by KClO_4 or $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ to a blue entity, Sb_3^{+2} . To this solution one might add a sufficient quantity of sulphur trioxide to make the composition, $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$. Thus the blue species have been stabilized in disulphuric acid. The colour, however, changes to yellow in case an excess of an oxidant is used. The molar absorptivities of the blue and yellow solutions register a maximum at oxidant/reductant ratios of 1 : 8 and 1 : 4 respectively and hence the stoichiometries of the cations Sb_3^{+2} and Sb_4^{+2} . The reactions are, however, the same as in the case of P_3^{+2} and P_4^{+2} .

The work on bismuth solutions is inconclusive as yet.

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